

HTR-10 Uncertainty Quantification and Comparison between ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5

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ABSTRACT

In this research, uncertainty quantification was conducted for HTR-10 using Serpent 2 to identify major uncertainty contributors among differential nuclear data. k_{eff} uncertainty with nuclear data from 2 recently-published libraries, ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5, was compared. The result demonstrated that total uncertainty due to nuclear data in ENDF/B-VIII.1 was 40 pcm larger than that of JENDL-5 (623 pcm vs. 583 pcm, respectively). Comparing individual reaction contribution to the total uncertainty, it was found that uncertainty due to U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ and χ were significantly different between the two libraries. For more accurate simulation of pebble bed High-Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (HTGR), evaluators for ENDF/B-VIII.1 should reduce statistical error of its U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ data in thermal region, whereas JENDL-5 evaluators should consider decreasing the statistical error of its U-235 χ data in the fast region.

Keywords: HTR-10, Serpent, ENDF/B-VIII.1, JENDL-5, Uncertainty Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear data is essential for reactor safety analysis. Bostelmann et al. had demonstrated that for HTR-10, the difference between ENDF/B-VII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 data is Δk_{eff} of 777 pcm [1]. Huang et al. showed that for HTR-10, difference between CENDL-3.2 and ENDF/B-VIII.0 data is $\Delta k_{\text{eff}} \approx 1000$ pcm [2].

The large difference in k_{eff} is caused by the combined effect of differences in differential nuclear data between libraries. Due to the lack of benchmark experiments, differential nuclear data were not calibrated for HTGR [3]. Therefore, it is crucial to determine which differential nuclear data contributes most significantly to the HTGR criticality uncertainty. Identifying the principal contributors to k_{eff} uncertainty will inform nuclear-data evaluators which differential datasets require higher-fidelity evaluation to reduce statistical errors. As additional HTGR benchmark experiments become available, targeted biasing of these differential nuclear data can be applied to mitigate bias and improve the accuracy of criticality calculations. Quantifying the disparity in HTR-10 k_{eff} uncertainty between ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 may serve as a reference framework for future comparisons of uncertainty quantification in pebble-bed reactors employing different nuclear data libraries.

This research studied uncertainty of HTR-10, a 10 MWth pebble-bed reactor built by the Institute of Nuclear and New Energy Technology (INET), Tsinghua University, in the early 2000s. The International Handbook of Evaluated Reactor Physics Benchmark Experiments (IRPhEP) includes evaluation of the initial critical configuration of HTR-10 [4]. The benchmark provided detailed geometry and material parameters, which are essential for Monte Carlo modeling and simulation. The benchmark also provides the experimental measurement of k_{eff} and sample calculation results of k_{eff} . This benchmark data is used as a validation of this research.

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The research evaluated the k_{eff} uncertainty difference between ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 nuclear data libraries. These two libraries contain data for a wide range of isotopes and are widely used by various neutron transport codes. Besides, both ENDF/B-VIII.1 (released in October 2024) [5], and JENDL-5 (released in December 2021) [6] were released recently and will benefit from further examination.

In this research, Serpent 2.1.32 from VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd (VTT) [7] was used to calculate the criticality of HTR-10 using ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5, respectively. In addition, ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 covariance matrices were processed by SCALE/AMPX and used in Serpent 2 to calculate k_{eff} uncertainty due to these nuclear data. The major k_{eff} uncertainty contributors for both libraries were identified for the HTR-10 reactor. Then, the difference in results were investigated in more detail to identify isotope, reaction type, and energy range which would benefit the most from additional evaluation effort.

2. METHODOLOGY

Section 2 describes how nuclear data was processed and how it was used to calculate k_{eff} uncertainty using Serpent 2.

2.1. Processing of nuclear data

The evaluated nuclear data was obtained from the Nuclear Data Services (NDS), International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). To keep consistency, original ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 point-wise ENDF-6 data was processed into ACE format using the From Evaluated Nuclear Data library to any application (FRENDY) code [8]. The ACE data was then used in Serpent 2 for criticality and uncertainty calculations.

The covariance data also had to be processed from ENDF-6 to Serpent-readable COVERX format. In this research we used the public version of AMPX-6 [9, 10] to process ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 covariance data into a 56 group covariance library in COVERX format. An important difference between the two libraries is that JENDL-5 does not have covariance data for C-12. However, Chen Hao et al. demonstrated that HTGR k_{eff} is sensitive to C-12 capture and elastic scattering cross section [11]. To make the uncertainty results from the two libraries consistent and comparable, C-12 covariance data from ENDF/B-VIII.1 was added to the covariance library of JENDL-5.

Correlation and standard deviation data were also extracted from AMPX in ASCII format to visualize the differences between two libraries. For energy groups X and Y , the correlation of nuclear data between group X and Y , $\text{Corr}(X, Y)$, can be calculated from the covariance between group X and Y $\text{Cov}(X, Y)$ and standard deviations $\text{std}(X)$ and $\text{std}(Y)$:

$$\text{Corr}(X, Y) = \frac{\text{Cov}(X, Y)}{\text{std}(X) \cdot \text{std}(Y)} \quad (1)$$

where the standard deviation of group X is the square root of the X -th entry in the diagonal of the covariance matrix:

$$\text{std}(X) = \sqrt{\text{Cov}(X, X)} \quad (2)$$

2.2. Uncertainty calculation using Serpent 2

Sensitivity coefficient (or simply sensitivity) S is the relative change in a response (in this case, k_{eff}) due to relative change in a perturbed quantity (in this case, nuclear data X):

$$S_X^{k_{\text{eff}}} = \frac{\frac{dk_{\text{eff}}}{k_{\text{eff}}}}{\frac{dX}{X}} = \frac{X}{k_{\text{eff}}} \frac{dk_{\text{eff}}}{dX} \quad (3)$$

The superscript for sensitivity will be omitted from now on for simplicity. Noting the nuclear data is dependent on energy, $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_X$ is also a function of energy. Serpent 2 uses a collision history-based approach to Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) to calculate multi-group sensitivity [12]. If the N_g -group relative covariance matrix $\overline{\overline{\text{Cov}}}_X \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times N_g}$ is provided for differential nuclear data X , and its N_g -group sensitivity vector $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_X \in \mathbb{R}^{N_g \times 1}$ is calculated, the covariance of k_{eff} caused by error in nuclear X , $\overline{\overline{\text{Cov}}}_X$, can be calculated by Serpent 2 using the first-order uncertainty propagation formula (sandwich rule):

$$\text{Cov}_X \approx (\bar{\mathbf{S}}_X)^T \overline{\overline{\text{Cov}}}_X (\bar{\mathbf{S}}_X) \quad (4)$$

and the propagated nuclear data uncertainty for k_{eff} is simply:

$$\text{Unc}_X = \sqrt{\text{Cov}_X} \quad (5)$$

2.3. Uncertainty comparison

This study studied the uncertainty contribution of U-235, U-238, C-12, and O-16. These 4 isotopes were selected because of their importance in neutronics: the fuel is composed of U-235, U-238, and O-16, and the moderator is C-12. Research by Chen Hao et al. has demonstrated that for HTR-10, the top sensitivity contributors come from U-235, U-238 and carbon. The studied reactions included:

1. MF=3, MT=1 (total cross section),
2. MF=3, MT=2 (elastic scattering cross section),
3. MF=3, MT=4 (inelastic scattering cross section),
4. MF=3, MT=18 (fission cross section),
5. MF=3, MT=102 (capture cross section),
6. MF=1, MT=456 (average number of prompt neutrons per fission $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$),
7. MF=1, MT=455 (average number of delayed neutrons per fission $\bar{\nu}_{\text{delay}}$),
8. MF=5, MT=18 (fission neutron energy spectrum χ).

In order to study and better understand energy-dependent contribution to uncertainty, the 56 group structure (based on SCALE[9]) was divided into three sub-regions:

1. Thermal: 0 to 1.13 eV
2. Resonance: 1.13 eV to 3.74 keV
3. Fast: Larger than 3.74 keV.

The thermal region was selected to cover at least 99% of thermal neutrons from the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The resonance region was selected to cover the unresolved resonance range for U-235, which ends at 2.25 keV in both libraries. The specific energy cutoffs were then selected to be consistent with the 56 group energy structure. Then, for energy region i (with $N_{X,i}$ energy intervals) in nuclear data X , and the partial sensitivity $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_{X,i} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{X,i} \times 1}$ (from Serpent 2 output) and partial covariance matrix $\overline{\overline{\text{Cov}}}_{X,i} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{X,i} \times N_{X,i}}$ (from AMPX output), the partial covariance $\text{Cov}_{X,i}$ is

$$\text{Cov}_{X,i} \approx (\bar{\mathbf{S}}_{X,i})^T \overline{\overline{\text{Cov}}}_{X,i} (\bar{\mathbf{S}}_{X,i}) \quad (6)$$

Assuming the correlation between any two energy region is close to 0, the sum of partial covariance should be close to the total covariance of reaction X :

$$\text{Cov}_X \approx \text{Cov}_{X,\text{thermal}} + \text{Cov}_{X,\text{resonance}} + \text{Cov}_{X,\text{fast}} \quad (7)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Criticality, sensitivity, and uncertainty were calculated for HTR-10. The criticality results are shown in Table I. Calculated k_{eff} using ENDF/B-VIII.1 was 356 pcm larger than that of JENDL-5. The top k_{eff} uncertainty contributors were identified and are compared and discussed in the following sections.

Table I. HTR-10 criticality using ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5.

Library	k_{eff}	k_{eff} Statistical Uncertainty (1σ)
ENDF/B-VIII.1	1.00563	10×10^{-5}
JENDL-5	1.00207	12×10^{-5}

3.1. Top contributors to k_{eff} uncertainty for HTR-10

The top six k_{eff} uncertainty contributors are tabulated in Table II in decreasing order. The total uncertainty (0.62%) is consistent with the results from Bolstelmann et al. (0.69%)[13]. The top 5 contributors are also consistent with the report. Uncertainty caused by ENDF/B-VIII.1 data is 7% larger than that of JENDL-5 data, primarily due to larger uncertainty in U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ in ENDF/B-VIII.1. It should be noted that the total uncertainty is the square root of total covariance, which is the sum of k_{eff} covariance caused by all differential nuclear data contributions.

 Table II. HTR-10: comparison of top k_{eff} uncertainty contributors between ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5.

Reaction type	ENDF/B-VIII.1 Unc. [pcm]	JENDL-5 Unc. [pcm]	$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\bar{\sigma}}$ [%]
U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$	447	303	38
C-12 Capture Cross Section	273	259	5
C-12 Elastic Scattering Cross Section	253	260	3
U-235 Fission Cross Section	171	174	2
U-235 χ	50	237	130
C-12 Inelastic Scattering Cross Section	43	50	15
Total	623	583	7

The results are qualitatively consistent with previously published results for gas-cooled, graphite-moderated thermal reactors [1, 2, 3].

3.2. Uncertainty difference in U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$

Table II shows that k_{eff} uncertainty due to U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ is significantly different between ENDF/B-VIII.1 (447 pcm) and JENDL-5 (303 pcm). From Eq. (4), k_{eff} uncertainty is proportional to both sensitivity and covariance matrix. The 56-group sensitivity and 56-group standard deviation of U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ is compared in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively. With both the 56-group sensitivity and 56-group relative covariance data available, it is possible to calculate the partial contribution to uncertainty due to U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ in thermal, resonance, and fast energy region, respectively, see Eqs. 6 and 7.

The results of $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ uncertainty contribution in the thermal, resonance, and fast energy regions are shown in Table III. It confirms that uncertainty in the thermal region is responsible for the majority of the difference. Figure 1 shows that thermal sensitivity for U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ is significantly larger than resonance and fast sensitivity for both libraries. Figure 2 shows that ENDF/B-VIII.1 relative standard deviation in the thermal regions is around 0.45% and JENDL-5 relative standard deviation in thermal region is around 0.31%, which is directly proportional to the "thermal" results shown in Table III.

The absolute value of U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ sensitivity is large in the thermal region for both ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5. The sensitivity does not differ significantly for the two libraries. The standard deviation of JENDL-5 U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ in the thermal region, on the other hand, is around 40% smaller than that of ENDF/B-VIII.1. The U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ k_{eff} uncertainty of JENDL-5 is around 140 pcm smaller than that of ENDF/B-VIII.1. This is caused by the smaller JENDL-5 U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ standard deviation in the fast

region, amplified by large U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{prompt}$ sensitivity in the fast region.

Figure 1. HTR-10 sensitivity for U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{prompt}$ (MF=1, MT=456) for ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5

Figure 2. U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{prompt}$ and its relative standard deviation for ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5

Table III. HTR-10 U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{prompt}$ partial uncertainty by energy group.

Library	Total [pcm]	Thermal [pcm]	Resonance [pcm]	Fast [pcm]
ENDF/B-VIII.1	447	429	19	1
JENDL-5	303	295	10	0.9
Difference	143	133	9	0.1

3.3. Uncertainty difference in U-235 χ

Table II shows that k_{eff} uncertainty due to U-235 χ is vastly different between ENDF/B-VIII.1 (50 pcm) and JENDL-5 (237 pcm). Similar to Section-3.2, the 56-group sensitivity and 56-group standard deviation of U-235 χ are compared in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The result of partial uncertainty in the three energy regions (thermal, resonance, fast) is shown in Table IV. Note that the energy in this section is the fission-emitted neutron energy, not incident neutron energy.

Figure 3. HTR-10 sensitivity for U-235 χ (MF=5, MT=18) for ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5

Figure 4. U-235 χ and its relative standard deviation for ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5

Table IV shows that the fast region is the dominant contributor to U-235 χ uncertainty. The majority of fission neutrons are produced in the fast region, and it is impossible for fission to emit low-energy neutrons, therefore uncertainty contribution from thermal regions is 0. This agrees with Figure 3, where U-235 χ (thermal, resonance, part of fast region) is effectively 0. On the other hand, Figure 4 shows that the U-235 χ relative standard deviation above 10 keV (fast region) is significantly larger in JENDL-5 than ENDF/B-VIII.1.

Table IV. HTR-10 U-235 χ partial uncertainty by energy group.

Library	Total [pcm]	Thermal [pcm]	Resonance [pcm]	Fast [pcm]
ENDF/B-VIII.1	50	0	2	40
JENDL-5	237	0	0.7	236
Difference	-187	0	1.3	-196

The absolute value of U-235 χ sensitivity is large in the fast region for both ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5. The sensitivity does not differ significantly for the two libraries. The standard deviation of JENDL-5 U-235 χ in the fast region, on the other hand, is 2 to 3 times larger than that of ENDF/B-VIII.1. The U-235 χ k_{eff} uncertainty of JENDL-5 is around 190 pcm larger than that of ENDF/B-VIII.1. This is caused by the larger JENDL-5 U-235 χ standard deviation in the fast region, amplified by the large U-235 χ sensitivity in fast region.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Uncertainty quantification of HTR-10 k_{eff} was conducted with nuclear data from ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 using Serpent 2. The results indicated that the total uncertainty due to nuclear data is around 600 pcm and the k_{eff} difference between the two libraries is only around 40 pcm. Uncertainty for U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ and χ is significantly different between the two libraries and in opposite direction relative to each other. For U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$, sensitivity dominates in the thermal region. U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ relative standard deviation of ENDF/B-VIII.1 in thermal region is around 40% larger than that of JENDL-5. For U-235 χ , sensitivity dominates in the fast region. U-235 χ relative standard deviation of JENDL-5 in fast region is around 2-3x larger than that of ENDF/B-VIII.1. Since these differences are in opposite direction, even though U-235 $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ thermal region is responsible for 130 pcm of uncertainty, and U-235 χ fast region is responsible for 190 pcm of uncertainty, the cumulative effect is that the total uncertainty difference between ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 is only 40 pcm.

NOMENCLATURE

- χ Fission neutron energy spectrum
- Cov_X k_{eff} covariance matrix due to error in differential nuclear data X
- $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_X$ Multi-group k_{eff} sensitivity vector for differential nuclear data X
- $\bar{\nu}_{\text{prompt}}$ Average number of prompt neutrons per fission
- $\overline{\overline{\text{Cov}_X}}$ Multigroup relative covariance matrix of differential nuclear data X

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